

МАДАНИЯТ ВА САЊАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE SUBJECT "MUSIC CULTURE" IN RAISING THE SPIRITUALITY OF STUDENTS

ANNOTATION

In this article, the importance of the science of music culture in our life, the history of its origin, and, at the same time, the promotion of youth interest in music, their love for music and musical aesthetic taste, and the education of young people in the spirit of love for the country. the role and importance of the science of culture will be discussed.

Key word: status, music, art, folklore, folk songs, musical instrument performance, aesthetic, tune, tone, rhythm, harmony, culture, personnel training.

O'QUVCHILAR MA'NAVIYATINI YUKSALTIRISHDA "MUSIQA MADANIYATI" FANINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Musiqa madaniyati fani bizning hayotimizda tutgan o'rni ahamiyati, kelib chiqish tarixi va shu bilan birgalikda yoshlarni musiqaga bo'lgan qiziqishlari, ularni musiqaga muhabbati va musiqiy estetik didlarini oshirish keng ko'lamda targ'ibot etish va yoshlarni vatanga muhabbat ruhida tarbiyalashda musiqqa madaniyati fanining o'rni va ahamiyati borasida so'z olib boriladi.

Kalit so'z: Maqom, musiqa, san'at, folklor, xalq qo'shiqlari, cholg'u ijrochiligi, estetik, kuy, ohang, ritm, garmoniya, madaniyat, kadrlar tayyorlash.

РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПРЕДМЕТА «МУЗЫКАЛЬНАЯ КУЛЬТУРА» В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ДУХОВНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается значение науки о музыкальной культуре в нашей жизни, история ее возникновения, а вместе с тем и воспитание интереса молодежи к музыке, ее любви к музыке и музыкально-эстетическому вкусу, воспитание молодежи в духе любви к Родине будут обсуждаться роль и значение науки о культуре.

Ключевые слова: статус, музыка, искусство, фольклор, народные песни, исполнительство на музыкальных инструментах, эстетика, мелодия, тон, ритм, гармония, культура, подготовка кадров.

The spiritual growth of our country is in many ways a deep understanding of the restoration of our national values, a wide-scale promotion with a heart, educating young people in the spirit of love for the motherland, and at the same time, the role and importance of the science of "music culture" in our lives. It is one of our important tasks to give an understanding of music, and most importantly, to awaken young people's love for music, to develop their knowledge potential. In this regard, our musical values have a special place. In particular, the folk music of the Uzbek people and the maqams, which are the creations of master artists, constitute the truly priceless spiritual wealth of our nation. In the musical samples of our time, the noble intentions, dreams and hopes, delicate emotional experiences and philosophical observations about existence in general are vividly expressed by our ancestors.

Therefore, when we listen to national songs, the "Voice of the Ages" sung by them, the delicate and high human feeling embodied in charming melodies, excites our native hearts and at the same time encourages us to appreciate our artistic traditions inherited from our forefathers. Fundamental reforms implemented in all spheres of our social life, including the various stages of the continuous education system, are closely related to the tasks of training pedagogues who meet the requirements of international standards in the training of highly qualified specialist personnel. However, the main goal of education is to educate a future music teacher with independent and creative thinking, high spirituality and culture, comprehensively developed professional-methodical training for general secondary schools. is one of the most important tasks of the people and the state.

It is unique from the teacher who realizes the formal tasks of developing preschoolers and students of general secondary schools as well-rounded individuals, forming music, which is an important component of their spiritual culture. professional-pedagogical and methodical training, high performance skills and professional pedagogical knowledge are required.

Effective use of all the educational, educational and developmental opportunities of musical art and music training, which is a factor in the formation of sophistication, beauty, high aesthetic feelings, and positive abilities in the hearts of young students, this process is implemented by the state organization at the level of educational standards requires sufficient professional training from the music teacher. Such a music teacher, who can meet the requirements of general and professional competence, is carried out by the training of bachelor personnel of the "Music Education" direction of higher educational institutions of pedagogy.

Further improvement of the higher education system, bringing it to the level of developed countries, increasing the quality and efficiency of training future pedagogues, organizing the educational process based on advanced foreign experiences is one of the strategic directions of the state policy conducted in our country.

Our people have great experience in the field of child education and training. In the history of our national education, the idea of human beauty and perfection was put forward by our great scholars such as Al-Beruni, Ibn-Sina, Ahmad Yassavi, Alisher Navai, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, Jalaluddin Rumi, and it was imprinted in the hearts of thousands of students.

R.A. Verkhola, V.S. Virchak, S.M.Dadajonov, E.I.Zamoshina, Q.M.Mamirov, O.Ibrahimov, D. in the field of comprehensive development of the young generation, the role of music in their aesthetic upbringing, forms, tools and methods of forming music in young students. Omonullyeva, Z.R.Rakhimova, H.Nurmatov, F.Khalilov, I.L.Smirnova, R.G'.Kadirov, T.I.Shevchenko, Q.B.Panjiyev and others, improving the professional training of future music teachers through Uzbek folk songs, etc. studied by

In addition to professional and methodological training of future music teachers in the field of "Music Education" in the field of higher educational institutions of the Republic of Pedagogy, folklore and folk songs are the national musical heritage. , improvement of professional training in musical performance can be recognized as an urgent issue of today.

This study guide covers the basics of the preparation of future music teachers for professional and methodical activities and the effective use of tools, methods and technologies in the successful implementation of education in music classes in general secondary schools.

The spiritual growth of our nation in many ways requires a deep understanding of the revival of our national values, a wide-scale promotion with heartfelt feelings, and most importantly, consistency in educating the young generation. In this regard, our musical values have a special place. In particular, the folk music of the Uzbek people and the maqams, which are the creations of master artists, represent the truly priceless spiritual wealth of our nation. In the musical samples of our time, the virtues, dreams and hopes, delicate emotional experiences and philosophical observations about the existence of our ancestors have been vividly expressed. Therefore, when we listen to national songs, the "Voice of the Centuries" sung by them excites our hearts with delicate and high human emotions embodied in charming melodies and at the same time encourages us to appreciate our artistic traditions inherited from our ancestors.

The goal is to fundamentally reform the education system, to educate a perfect person who is mature in all respects, rich, who embodies mental purity and physical stability. The main factor in solving these historical tasks is a complex and multifaceted comprehensive educational system. Studying our national music and culture deeper and more carefully than ever before, conveying and promoting it to the young generation is one of the urgent issues facing us artists.

The content of music is impressions of life, thoughts and feelings expressed through sounds. The expression of the content through sound is subject to certain rules that connect the means of expression of music. These rules emerged as a result of the centuries-old experience of folk and classical music.

It is important to manage the social activity of a person's spiritual world, sensitive feelings, inner experiences. The role of our national music, including status and art, is incomparable and enormous in balancing the perfect spiritual elation and strange feelings. Our ancestors praised the power of our music for centuries and enjoyed it in their relationships, work activities, and social life.

Being musically literate has its specific goals and objectives. In the implementation of this, the existing national methods set a certain direction. Mastering music, listening, playing and using it in life. Interests are combined with human culture. Statuses, which are considered to be one of the masterpieces created by our people, are expressed to a certain extent in education, work and social relations. Murgak can enjoy the blessings of art from babies to enlightened old people. They fight for a brighter tomorrow.

Music is an independent field with great educational opportunities in our country. Now, thanks to the reforms carried out by our honorable president Shavkat Miramanovich Mirziyayev, the attractive and lively scope of music, its position will expand even more, and its place won in society will be strengthened. In the process of education, music is the basis of moral and aesthetic education of the young generation. A number of accelerations and efficiency of the educational process will increase.

At a time when fundamental reforms in the economic, political and social spheres are being carried out in our country after the first stages of the Great Independence, special attention is being paid to humane and progressive factors such as national culture and art, spirituality and enlightenment.

In this place, it is extremely important to fully restore our ancient and invaluable values, our folk customs and traditions, to study our historical and cultural monuments, including our musical heritage in detail. It should be recognized that all the necessary conditions have been created in recent years for its scientific and practical assimilation by young generations. Melody is an expression of the divine mood in the human soul. The idea and imagination of a real work first appears in the imagination, and then comes to life due to the performance and becomes a specific melody. The life of the melody is very short; as soon as it appears, it escapes and disappears. But an impressive sound, a melody leaves a deep mark in the heart of the listener and invites to aspire to this pleasant state again.

One of the simplest ways to preserve the sound of the melody is to share the situation that has arisen in the heart with close souls. If the first melody of the melody is accepted, if it has an effect without remaining indifferent, the desire to continue this pleasure will be awakened. In this mental state, the hearts of the performer and the listener are connected, they get the same nourishment from the melody, and a harmonious musical process is created from such a connection of emotions, and the artist becomes the creator, and the listener becomes his fans.

The art of music, which has a centuries-old history, has served as an important tool in the education and development of a person. The Uzbek people have rich traditions in all fields that have been created over many centuries and are passed down from generation to generation. Education of individual spirituality through music is one of the main traditions of our nation.

At present, we are proud of our scientists, historical monuments, musical heritage, and, in general, our huge material and spiritual heritage, which are recognized by the whole world. It is our duty to learn, implement and preserve this heritage and pass it on to the next generation. Accordingly, it is impossible to be a cultured person without knowing the history of culture.

The music of the Uzbek people has a long tradition. The music of the ancestors of the Uzbek people is closely related to the creativity of the brotherly peoples who lived with them until the 10th-11th centuries. From this period, the musical heritage created by these nations served as a common basis for the formation of music later.

As early as the 4th century BC, the Greek philosopher Plato said about the influence of music on a person and its educational importance: "The greatest educational scientist is musical art. After all, if education is carried out correctly, rhythm and harmony will find the deepest way to the soul and give strength, make it beautiful, otherwise, it will turn out to be its opposite. says. In fact, the art of music serves as a means of education in any human society. This opinion is confirmed once again by the flourishing of science and culture in the Middle Ages.

Summary

Music art, like works of art, leads a person to high spiritual values, introduces him to strange melodies and sounds from a young age. A child learns to hear and feel music to a certain extent even when he does not know how to hold a pencil, read and draw. Often, these first impressions can play an important role in the formation of people's attitudes towards music. Therefore, in the main areas of reform of general education and vocational schools, issues of fundamental change of educational work in music and general secondary education schools have also been advanced.

First of all, music educates children's aesthetic worldview, awakens such qualities as feeling a work of art, expressing one's attitude to them. Of course, literature, sports, history, and other fields play an important role in developing these qualities. In this place, poetry and music always live side by side and complement each other.

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